

The Signification of Color in Balinese Art and Culture

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ABSTRACT

Color is very essential in life; it is hard to imagine this world without color. All colors appear between black and white because they exist due to the effects of light. Color is a reflection of human nature, with characteristics that all have their respective meanings. This article focuses on the significant meaning of how to use color in Balinese art and culture. The color of the Balinese mandala in the form of a color wheel plays a magical, religious, and symbolic role based on Hindu philosophy. Each direction is represented by a color, meaning, God, place in the body, day, and number. The meaning of color in Balinese art, philosophy, religion, customs, traditions, and culture is a series of processes of exploring the inner and outer balance of life, macrocosmos, and microcosmos. The method used is observation and interviews, the results of which are used for offerings to the five elements of nature, which are reflected in the purification ceremony with various levels of sacrificial offerings to the spirits of nature. This process can be seen in the purification ceremony of new buildings called *melaspas*. *Melaspas* is a process of cleansing, purification, and awakening the spirit to live. The color of flowers is part of a very significant, symbolic sacredness used in various forms of religious rituals. Color as decoration has a symbolic aesthetic value installed in sacred places. A shadow puppet is a reflection of a life that is not only seen from its form and attributes, but the role of color is very decisive in seeing the character itself. The *tridatu* color as a bracelet is a symbol of protection. Sacred songs explain the existence of that color with all forms and manifestations of God's light. *Lawar* is food for offerings; each color represents certain elements to maintain the balance of the universe.

Keywords: color, art, and culture.

I. Introduction

Color is light, something very simple, a daily need, and none of us can live without light. Color is a direct function of light and represents all aspects of life. The circle of primary colors (red, yellow, and blue), secondary colors (orange, green, and violet), and their mixing to give rise to tertiary colors is a broad understanding of conventional colors. Color is also associated with warm-cold temperatures. Warm colors (yellow, orange, and red) and cool colors (green, blue, and violet). In general, color is widely used as a sign, symbol, icon, and visual communication medium.

In Bali, the meaning of color is very significant because it represents shapes and symbols in everyday life, which are based on the philosophy of Hinduism. Color is associated with philosophy, mythology, offerings, and aesthetics in art, customs, and cultural practices. Bali is an art island that has a variety of arts and cultures, such as literary

arts (*lontar*), theater/performance arts (dance, *gamelan*, puppetry), fine arts (painting, sculpture, craft, wood/stone carving, metal, leather, weaving, and recording media arts (photography, film, and television).

The Balinese mandala is a local color circle associated with the balance and harmony of the Universe. Each direction has a color, god, place in the body, day, animal, and weapon. On other hand, color in Balinese art and culture also given the many types of names from nature, as the limited number of words to name colors, local terms also appear for color names, for example, young banana leaf color, red brick, water apple, red pomegranate, blue sky, yellow *waru* flower, light brown sapodilla, ripe papaya, and others.

II. Philosophical Foundation

A. Literature

The book *Shilpa Shastra*, described by Shashikala Ananth (2016), argues that the

science of arts and crafts is an ancient guideline for Hindu religious texts that explain arts, crafts, and their standard principles (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Shilpa_Shastras). Shilpa Shastra is a guidebook to create arts, crafts, architecture, etc. Vaastu Shastra fundamentally explains that the basics of good and true art, namely: 1) *bhogadyam* (usability), 2) *sukha darsham* (aesthetics), 3) *ramya* (inner satisfaction), and spiritual satisfaction. In Hindu philosophy, God is said to have three attributes: *satyam* (truth), *sivam* (holiness), and *sundaram* (beauty).

Regarding the color philosophy of the Balinese mandala, there are four cardinal principal colors: east direction is white, Lord Iswara; red to the south, Lord Brahma; yellow to the west, Lord Mahadewa; and black to the north, Lord Vishnu. In addition to the four main colors, there are also other colors, namely: pink in the southeast of Lord Maheswara, orange in the southwest of Lord Rudra, green in the northwest of Lord Sangkara, and gray/blue in the northeast of Lord Sambhu. In the middle of the five colors (a combination of the four main colors) is Lord Shiva.

Fig. 1. The Gods in each direction.
Sumber foto: Dokumentasi penulis (2020).

B. Color in the body

Ngurah Nala (1996) in his book *Usada Bali*, explains that according to the teachings of Tantra, in the human body there are seven chakras, the control centers of life, which in other books or teachings vary in number, color, and are also referred to as medicine or therapy. In the *Kundalini Tantra* (2012) the

writings of Swami Satyananda Saraswati describe that the seven principal chakras as follows: 1) root chakra (*mooladhara*) - dark red lotus; 2) sacral chakra (*swadhisthana*) - vermillion lotus; 3) solar plexus chakra (*manipura*) – yellow lotus; 4) heart chakra (*anahata*) – blue lotus; 5) throat chakra (*vishuddhi*) - violet lotus; .6) third eye chakra (*ajna*) – silver ash lotus; 7) crown chakra (*sahasrara*) – multicolored or red lotus.

Fig. 2 Color of the chakra
(<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Lju6h-C37hE> (cited 30 August 2021).

Gradually, we can see in the daily practice of art and culture all of the above references as the roots and soul of a culture. There are two types of belief systems regarding direction. First, the Balinese believe that the east is the starting point for calculating mandala circles. Second, the north direction is the starting point for calculating the direction. Both are correct in terms of the Balinese belief system; the first is based on sunrise (the sun is the source of energy), the second is based on higher elevations such as mountains or hills (mountains are the place of God). The main idea is the balance between macro and microcosmos, human beings, and the Universe.

III. The Signification of Colors in Balinese Art and Culture.

According to Western knowledge, the spectrum According to Western knowledge, the spectrum of sunlight passes through a prism and scatters into different colors, but in Balinese culture, color occupies each cardinal

direction according to the energy of the gods. The existence of color as a bridge between the material world and the spiritual world, from color material pigments to the light, from concrete to abstract. Color is a representation of natural objects, as the eye sees objects as they are. Color also has arbitrary properties according to the user's will, for example, the color of the sky, sea, plants and other natural objects are colored according to the artist's inner content, not like the colors we see in nature. Color also has its function, it does not represent anything or anyone, except for the color itself, for example, red as red/spirit of red, not associated with other objects or emotions. However, in Balinese art and culture, the dominant color plays a symbolic role, especially in Hindu philosophy.

Life, art, and culture are closely related to Balinese colorful ornate offerings; the creation of color starts from the artist's anxiety, which is done by clearing the mind. That restlessness penetrates deep into the conscience, the interaction of the artist with the universe. Furthermore, the creative process brings into the realm of silence, the sublime, and nothingness. That is one of the processes of spirituality in the creation of works of art to emit the light of the beauty of Balinese colors.

Color as a sign and symbol of protection. In Balinese Hindu belief, people generally wear the *tridatu* color on their hands as a symbol of protection. *Tridatu* is three main colors in Balinese culture: red, black, and white. All three colors symbolized the energy of Brahma, Vishnu, and Shiva as the circle of life, birth, and death. The sign of the cross (+) is often symbolized as protection in white color, also used for healing, as the balance of all four directions, macro-microcosmos, human, God, and nature. Color is healing (Norris, 2001).

Fig. 3. *Tridatu* color on the bracelet as a protection symbol. Sumber foto: Dokumentasi penulis (2020).

Color is used as an identity and characteristic of a culture. Balinese color has a specificity with symbolic value in it. The painting also often displays colors in part of the Bali mandala colors, so it is clear that the color circle is a feature of Balinese art.

Wayang, as a "shadow" reflection of life, is not only seen from its shape and attributes, but the role of color is very decisive in seeing the character of the figure itself. Likewise, in coloring the skin of each figure, it is adjusted to the character of the figure. Color is a reflection of the character and traits that are portrayed. In the Balinese shadow puppet, each color represents the character of the figure. For example, Khrisna is the avatar of Wisnu, as the God of water, the color presentation is blue/green. Dharmawangsa represents truth, as purity, and the color is white. Arjuna is a warrior, representing the best aspects of humanity: courage, strength, intelligence, and wisdom. The color presentation is amber. *Tualen* is symbolic of wisdom, lots of experiences, an elder, old soul, humorous, and the color is dark brown.

Fig. 4. Balinese shadow puppet. Sumber foto: Dokumentasi penulis (2020).

Pasupati or *pangurip-urip* is a process of clearing, purifying, and awakening the spirit to be alive, for example, in the *melaspas* ceremony of the construction of new buildings. *Melaspas* is a blessing or purifying ceremony applied to all the aspects of Balinese Hinduism, such as temples, buildings, artifacts, etc., before it uses. In *pangurip-urip*, traditional colors are used: limestone/*pamor* is used for white in the east, animal blood (chicken or duck) is used for red, turmeric is used for yellow, and charcoal is used for black. Color is not only for beauty but also for truth and goodness.

The color of flowers is part of a very significant, symbolic sacredness used in various forms of religious rituals. When there is a religious ceremony, the holy place is decorated, and the color attributes of the Balinese Mandala are according to the cardinal directions. When the priest makes holy water, placing the color of flowers according to the cardinal directions, and accompanied by holy songs that explain the existence of that color with all forms and manifestations of God's color light.

Fig. 5. The color direction in holy water. Sumber foto: Dokumentasi penulis (2020).

Fig. 6. Balinese offering. Sumber foto: Dokumentasi penulis (2020).

Fig. 7. Color and time. Sumber foto: Dokumentasi penulis (2020).

The symbolic colors, as stated in the Balinese color mandala, are also applied to the traditional food dish called *lawar*. *Lawar* is processed with various types of vegetables, meat, coconut, herbs, and spices, which are combined into a single unit according to the desired taste. The philosophical meaning of making *lawar* is to mix various taste elements from nature, such as salt in the sea, vegetables in the mountains, and meat as well as various kinds of flavors that are combined into a balanced Balinese taste. There are several *lawar* dishes in traditional forms which use five colors in their presentation. White *lawar*, red *lawar*, yellow *lawar*, and dark *lawar*/green leaves or long beans, and meat-dominant *lawar*.

The color in the offering ceremony of the five elements in nature is reflected in the purification (*mecaru*) ceremony, with various levels of sacred sacrifices offered to the spirits of nature. Purification is an offering ceremony to maintain the balance of the universe. In this ceremony, the fluids are used as follows: *tuak*/palm wine as white, *arak*/rice wine as yellow, *brem*/black rice wine as black, holy

water as colorless/silence, blood as red (Sudarsana, 2001). These five fluids are symbols of the water in the human body: spleen, gastric fluid, guts, bile, serum, and blood. All elements of offerings are associated with the colors in the cardinal directions.

Colors as decorations that have symbolic aesthetic value are installed in holy places or sacred places. The installation of Balinese fabric (Bandem, 1996) in holy places also follows the color of the cardinal directions. Likewise, the placement of fabric with certain colors on large trees, rocks, and certain places. All installations of fabric and other decorations, such as shade, flags, and ceremonial attributes, are related to understanding the colors and energies of the universe.

Flowers and water in Balinese culture are symbols of purity and life. The flower's color, besides being a mirror of beauty and purity, also has a symbolic meaning in the context of increasing spiritual awareness. For example, when the priest makes holy water, the placement of flower colors according to the cardinal directions is accompanied by sacred songs, lyrics, and songs explaining the existence of the colored lights of the gods in all directions of the compass.

The color meaning of the cardinal points reflects the aura, vibration, character, and properties of the color. The white color in the east has the meaning of purity, beginning, silence, clarity, absence, compassion, sincerity, cleanness, and colorlessness. The red color in the south has the meaning of courage, love, glory, anger, feelings, enthusiasm, burning, hot, fierce, explosive, and dynamic. Yellow in the west has the meaning of majesty, glory, golden, nobility, affection, cheerful, bright, intuitive, and warm. The black color black in the north has the meaning of loneliness, being late, being dark, being absent, being colorless, death, wisdom, being empty, and mysterious. The pink color in the southeast has the meaning of love, sweetness, affection, femininity, gentleness, and delicacy. The color orange in the southwest has the meaning of being tough, loving, cheerful, intelligent, warm, and comfortable. The color green in the northwest has the meaning of fertility, peace, growth, life, development, calm, freshness, sensation,

and awakening energy. The color gray/blue in the northeast has the meaning of knowledge, broad-minded, peaceful, cool, calm, cold, sad, gloomy, thinking, and intellectual. While the color in the middle is representative of the colors white, red, yellow, and black, which is called multicolor. Multicolor contains a symbolic meaning, which is to unite various colors in one container so that they have aesthetic, harmonious, balanced, and peaceful values. The gold color is very dominant in its use to show the impression of majesty/luxury, glory, which is generally combined with red or black.

Symbolic colors can be used as a medium in various aspects of Balinese art and culture, including in the process of internalization, the silence of the mind and soul, psychological therapy, meditation, and healing. Color is believed to be used to clear the mind, increase awareness, and patience in understanding characters and emotions. Based on belief, *chakra* color is within, occupies certain organs of the body, and affects feelings/emotions. The deepest experience of beauty as a starting point for artistic creativity underlies the activity of using color. The process of understanding and appreciating color in Balinese art and culture is a liaison between self-awareness and the universe. With the light of color rises cosmic consciousness, the disappearance of darkness, the emergence of Divine light. Sublimation and the highest color culmination point are a reflection of the union of Atman and Brahman.

The climate is a tropical land with bright colors, and the contrast between light and dark is also a significant influence on the use of color practice, both in art and culture.

IV. Conclusion

Color is a medium to awaken human consciousness related to the Universe, to maintain inner and outer balance. Color is a bridge between the physical and spiritual world, from the art and culture practice into the ideological, philosophical, and symbolical realms. In Balinese art and culture, color has significant meaning both in symbolic Hindu practice as well on the daily use of colors as a natural way of using color in a tropical climate. Color is enlivening the spirit of balance, harmony, and aesthetics in the macro

and microcosmos. Color is life, therefore to use color is to make it alive.

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